

Library "window of jogja" an inside librarian's idea "Memayu Hayuning Bawono" for Yogyakarta special region, Indonesia

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Abstract

Yogyakarta is a Special Region in Indonesia. It is special because it has characteristics that other regions do not have. Special as a city of culture, city of education, city of students, city of tourism, city of history, city of warriors. Yogyakarta has many historical heritages, both in physical form and cultural traditions, that must be preserved. Yogyakarta still needs facilities that describe all the existing privileges. There are also no libraries in Yogyakarta that present Yogyakarta's treasures as a whole. Librarians must think about preservation efforts, *Memayu Hayuning Bawono*, for the specialty of Yogyakarta. Building a "Window of Jogja" library and community empowerment becomes an alternative for collecting, preserving, introducing, presenting, and promoting to the community and the outside world. The "Window of Jogja" library is a miniature of Yogyakarta or Taman Mini Yogyakarta. Community empowerment by involving all activities in preserving culture and special values with harmony and balance that make Yogyakarta beautiful and *ayu*.

Keywords: Indonesia, Window of Jogja, *Memayu Hayuning Bawono*, Special Region of Yogyakarta

Introduction

Yogyakarta... As soon as you hear Yogyakarta, your heart will feel at peace, and your mind will drift away, imagining a safe, comfortable, peaceful, and beautiful city. A city with all its characteristics, such as a cultural city, student city, tourist city, *Gudeg* city, warrior city, and many more names that can be given to Yogyakarta. Some say that Yogyakarta is also a miniature Indonesia. In this city live various kinds of people with ethnic backgrounds diverse. However, the cultural diversity in Yogyakarta can combine beautifully without triggering significant conflict.

In Yogyakarta, people with various social and educational backgrounds can mix harmoniously. Many great intellectuals, artists, and cultural figures have honed their knowledge in Yogyakarta. It is not surprising because Yogyakarta is also called the city of education. Hundreds of state universities and private universities are mushrooming in the city of Yogyakarta. Big names such as Affandi, Bagong Kussudiardjo, Umar Kayam, Emha Ainun Najib, Amien Rais, Mahfud MD and Sheila on 7, Jikustik, Letto, and Hudson, even JokoWi, who is now the most talked about person in Indonesia, have lived in Yogyakarta. Remember the song "Yogyakarta"? KLa Project, who is not from Yogyakarta, also wrote a song about Yogyakarta, and to this day, the music is still good to listen to and is often played everywhere.

In the Yogyakarta Mayor's Regulations Based on the 2005-2025 Regional Long Term Development Plan, the vision of the City of Yogyakarta is the City of Yogyakarta as a City of Quality Education, Culture-Based Tourism, and Service Center which is Environmentally Friendly. Yogyakarta City Development Vision 2005-

It is hoped that 2025 will realize the wishes and mandate of the City of Yogyakarta while still referring to the achievement of national goals as mandated in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, especially for the people of the

City of Yogyakarta. The Yogyakarta City Development Vision must be measurable to determine the level of success in making "Yogyakarta City a City of Quality Education, Culture-Based Tourism and Service Center, with an Environmental Insight."

What is meant by "Quality Education City" is:

1. The provision of education in the City of Yogyakarta must have high-quality standards and be leading in Southeast Asia;
2. Have a competitive advantage in mastering, utilizing, and developing technological knowledge;
3. Able to create a balance between intelligence (Intelligentia Quotient), emotional (Emotional Quotient), spiritual (Spiritual Quotient);
4. Developed with the support of a superior education policy system;
5. Provision of adequate educational facilities and infrastructure;
6. Creating a conducive educational atmosphere.

"Culture Based Tourism" is:

1. Tourism activities in the City of Yogyakarta are developed based on and centered on Javanese culture, which is in harmony with the history and culture of the Ngayogyakarta Hadiningrat Palace, local wisdom, and the noble values of national culture;
2. Perfect and increase the tourism cooperation network with other parties;
3. Become a leading tourist destination in Southeast Asia;
4. Increasing tourism activities is carried out by creating innovations that remain based on cultural tourism, historical building tourism, educational tourism, convection tourism, and shopping tourism;
4. Maintain and develop religious/religious norms in community life.

"Service Center" is

1. The city of Yogyakarta as a service center, which includes education and tourism support services, trade, government, finance, health, transportation, and communication, must be built to be more advanced and independent;
2. Provide more outstanding contribution and dominance than other regions in the Southern Java region;
3. Increasing service activities are carried out by strengthening the city's economy in mainstay sectors towards competitive advantage;
4. Building interconnected production, distribution, and service systems while maintaining and developing small and medium industries. "Environmentally Conscious" is:
 1. Conscious, planned, and sustainable efforts
 2. Integrating the natural environment with religious, social, cultural values and local wisdom into the development process;
 3. Guarantee current and future generations' capabilities, welfare, and quality of life.

In realizing the development vision of the City of Yogyakarta, this is achieved through 9 (nine) development missions as follows:

1. Maintaining the title of the City of Yogyakarta as an Education City, namely by seeking the participation of all components of society, local government, and the private sector so that the provision of education in the City of Yogyakarta has high-quality standards and is leading in Southeast Asia, has a competitive advantage that is highly competitive, high competence, pressing various negative influences that can damage the educational image of the City of Yogyakarta; creating superior education systems and policies; assist in providing educational facilities and infrastructure.
2. Maintaining the title of Yogyakarta City as a City of Tourism, City of Culture, and City of Struggle, namely by increasing tourist objects and attractions; displays landmarks (tetenger/monumental features) and typical culture of the City of Yogyakarta as well as the noble values of national culture; developing a tourism cooperation network with various parties; building adequate tourism facilities and infrastructure; creating government policies that support the development of urban tourism; increasing awareness and participation of all city residents in tourism development; carry out effective tourism promotion and marketing, so that it becomes one of the leading tourism destinations in Southeast Asia.
3. Realizing the competitiveness of the City of Yogyakarta, which is superior in services through increasing the growth of regional economic development by strengthening the city's economy based on the advantages of each mainstay sector towards competitive advantage by building linkages between production, distribution, and service systems, especially in services which include services.
Supporting education and tourism, trade, government, finance, health, transportation, and communication, reducing social inequality as a whole. Favoring the economy of the people, groups, and regions that are still weak, overcoming poverty drastically, providing equal access for urban communities to various social services

- and economic facilities and infrastructure, and equal opportunities in doing business and eliminating discrimination in various aspects, including gender; prioritizing the development of quality and competitive human resources, so that it can become a service center in the Southern Java region.
4. Realizing a comfortable and environmentally friendly Yogyakarta City by improving the management of development implementation that can maintain a balance between utilization and sustainability of the existence and use of natural resources and the environment while maintaining function, carrying capacity and capacity, comfort in life now and in the future. Front, through harmonious use of space; sustainable economic use of natural resources and the environment; managing natural resources and the environment for quality of life, providing beauty and comfort in life; and maintaining and utilizing biodiversity as an essential capital for development.
5. Creating a moral, ethical, civilized, and cultured Yogyakarta City society through increasing the integrity of every person in the city's community, strengthening the identity and character of the city's people who are devoted to God Almighty, obedient and obeying legal regulations; maintaining harmony and tolerance in society and between religious communities; develop a family spirit; enforce norms. Social norms, politeness, decency, and religious norms; carry out intercultural interactions; developing social life; implementing the noble values of the City of Yogyakarta; and have pride as a citizen of the City of Yogyakarta to strengthen the spiritual, moral and ethical foundations of city development.
6. Realizing the City of Yogyakarta with good governance, clean government, justice, democracy, and based on law by establishing more vital democratic institutions; strengthening the role of civil society; improving the quality of implementation of decentralization and regional autonomy; guaranteeing the development and freedom of communication media for the benefit of the city community; improve institutional structures and improve the culture of legal order; non-discriminatory; gender justice and side with the little people.
7. Realizing a safe, orderly, united, and peaceful Yogyakarta city through creating conducive conditions, maintaining and guaranteeing a safe, tidy, comfortable, and friendly situation by utilizing all components of society, government, and law enforcement officials so that they can protect and protect the community, preventing crime, and decide on criminal acts; building security stability and creating urban order;
8. Realizing the development of quality facilities and infrastructure through advanced infrastructure development by increasing the mastery, utilization, and creation of science and technology; advancing the carrying capacity of the city by developing and utilizing regional assets, city facilities, and infrastructure as well as public facilities that all levels of society can use;
9. Realizing a Healthy Yogyakarta City through providing adequate health services, good health facilities and infrastructure, a sound urban public health policy and system, quality human resources for health services, and highly competent and supported by community

Participation. Based on the Yogyakarta City Regional Long Term Development Plan, Librarianship in the perspective of Yogyakarta's privileges Librarians and Jogja's Specialties

1. Library in Yogyakarta

As a city of education, city of culture, and a tourist city, Yogyakarta has many libraries ranging from college libraries, school libraries, public libraries include the Yogyakarta Regional Library and Archives Agency (BPAD), City Libraries, Regency Libraries, and Special Libraries. The library is a facility that is very much needed in the development of the world of education. The story of the world of education will be complicated if it is not supported by the learning facilities required for teaching and learning activities.

Libraries are the primary source of obtaining information, which is the fundamental foundation for the progress of an institution, especially educational institutions, and the demand for adaptation to information developments is very high (Suwarno, 2010) [9]. This aligns with the Vision and Mission of the Regional Library and Archives Agency as the supervisor and tasked with developing and educating people's lives, namely "Creating a Learning Society with Character and Culture." This is stated in the 2012 – 2017 Mission

1. Improving Optimal Management and Utilization of Libraries and Archives.
2. Developing an Information Technology-based Library and Archives Network.
3. Realizing Libraries and Archives as regional cultural treasures. (<http://www.bpadjogja.info/visi-misi-bpad.html>)

By looking at the background of the city of Yogyakarta, with various names as a beautiful city, the Regional Library has yet to be able to provide services and facilities that show the uniqueness of Yogyakarta as a whole. So, on this occasion, as a librarian, I am called to preserve and uphold the unique features of Yogyakarta, starting from heritage sites, cultural customs, food, and the obligation to civilize and promote these specialties to the community. So that unique values will be well maintained and can be preserved by future generations. As librarians, we offer the library to create a design about Yogyakarta as a whole with the "Window of Jogja."

Literature Review

1. *Memayu Hayuning Bawono*

Forward comes from the root word "*Mayu*" which means beautiful, beautiful, or safe. Because it has the prefix "*Me-*" "*Memayu*" can be interpreted as beauty, beauty, or safety. "*Hayung*" can be interpreted as inviting, trying, preserving, or guarding. While the word *Hell* has a broad meaning, in simple terms, it can be interpreted as "ourselves/individuals," and externally, it can be interpreted as "Life/World/Universe." So *Memayu Hayuning Bawono* can be interpreted as we live in this world and should always try to maintain the safety of our lives and those around us.

Another source said that moving across the continent is a philosophy or noble value about life from Java culture. Across the continent, they interpreted in Indonesian to beautify the beauty of the world. Javanese people view this

concept not only as a philosophy of life but also as a character that everyone must have. Philosophy across the continent is also strongly felt in the teachings *kejawen*.

Memayu Hayuning Bawana has relevance to insight Javanese cosmology or Javanese cosmology. *Kejawen* has insight into kosmos, which is nothing but the embodiment of the concept across the continent.[1] *Memayu* is a continent that is a matter of space culture or cultural space and, at the same time, spiritual culture or cultural spirituality. Viewed from the side space culture, this expression contains a series of spaces or bring. Continents world with its contents. Continents is the cosmological region of Java. As a region of the cosmos, *Bawana* is seen as a world frame. *Jagad* frame is where humans live in reality. Contents are plants, fields, and, at the same time, gardens that live after death. People whose lives are in an inworld frame instilling goodness will later reap the rewards. Besides that, across the continental, a cultural spirituality. Cultural spirituality is an expression of culture done by the Javanese in the middle *jagad* rame (space culture). At this level, Javanese people live the spiritual practices that always adorn the world's welfare. The reality of living in an inworld frame is the need to suppress your desires so that they are more controlled and the world becomes more focused. The reality of life is, of course, that there is bargaining, bias, and profit and loss. Only noble people can reap benefits in the realities of life. In such processes, Javanese people often carry out science and chat to achieve a peaceful continent or world peace. This situation is what is meant as It or safely without any disturbance whatever. The Javanese encoded this atmosphere into expressions across the continent.

Moving across the continent is indeed an effort to protect the safety of the world, both physically and mentally. Javanese people feel obliged to cross the continental to beautify the world's beauty; this is the only thing that gives meaning to life. In one literal physical, man must maintain and improve their physical environment. Meanwhile, on the other hand, in the abstract, humans must also maintain and improve their spiritual environment. This view encourages that human life cannot be separated from the environment. Javanese people say humans should be environmentally wise, not destroy or do arbitrary things. (http://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Memayu_hayuning_bawana).

In Javanese society, especially in Yogyakarta, *Hayuning Bawana* has contributed to the education and character development of the younger generation (Darling *et al.*, 2020) [3]

2. Specialties of Yogyakarta

Istimewa /is·ti·me·wa//exception/a one typical (for specific purposes, etc.); unique: schools -- established for deaf and speech-impaired children; 2 another dp another; Extraordinary: in that city, he was welcomed --; 3 especially; more: he is good at drawing, -- landscape pictures; privilege /meng·is·ti·me·wa·kan/make (look, treat, etc.) unique: it is always ~ his lover; *teristimewa* /ter·is·ti·me·wa/a 1 The main; especially; mainly; 2 remarkable; very particular; *keistimewaan* /ke·is·ti·me·wa·an/n unique properties (<http://kbbi.web.id/istimewa>).

The uniqueness of the Special Region of Yogyakarta is reflected in various objects of view, including history, geography, economics, socio-cultural, spatial planning, and government. From a historical point of view, Yogyakarta's speciality is that it is an area that had legitimate authority

even before Indonesia became independent. So that Yogyakarta has regional autonomy rights that are different from other regions and stated in Article 18 of the 1945 Constitution. Meanwhile, geographically, its position is in the Central-South part of Java Island at 7°3'-8°12'S and 110°00'-110°50' East Longitude (Mansur *et al.*, 2021)^[5].

The D. I. Yogyakarta region is grouped into four physiographic units: the Mount Merapi physiographic unit, the Southern Mountains or Seribu Mountains, the Kulon Progo Mountains, and the Lowlands. These conditions affect population distribution, the availability of regional infrastructure and facilities, and the socio-economic activities of the population. In terms of the economy, several sectors that dominate the Yogyakarta region include investment, trade, agriculture, forestry, plantations, fisheries, energy, mineral resources, and tourism sectors. Meanwhile, in terms of spatial planning, Yogyakarta's diverse natural landscape and aspects of its cultural philosophy influence the development of spatial planning and infrastructure development in Yogyakarta (Aksa *et al.*, 2019)^[1]. The model used in DIY spatial planning is corridor development or "concentrating the intensity of human activity in a certain corridor," which focuses on the city of Yogyakarta and the roads around it. In this context, controlling and directing development are carried out more prominently in priority corridors regarding private investment activities, compared to development investment by the government, which must be controlled. Finally, regarding government, Yogyakarta was previously a Sultanate and Duchy (Aksa *et al.*, 2019)^[1].

Article 18 of the 1945 Constitution: Regional division into large and small regions, with the form of government structure determined by law taking into account and remembering the basic deliberations in State Government sessions and rights of origin in particular areas (Amos & Abraham, 2005)^[2]. Further, regarding the form of a unique government system, it is contained in Law Number 22 of 1948, which explains that Yogyakarta is a Special Region led by the Governor (Sultan) and the Deputy Governor, like other provinces with only remarkable features.

Result and Discussion

Yogyakarta as a Special Region. A city with many privileges that other regions do not have. Specialties include culture, customs, history, education, tourism, art, etc. Cultural heritage that must be preserved. From the vision and mission of Yogyakarta, we will emphasize two things: Yogyakarta as an Education City and Yogyakarta as a Culture-based Tourism City.

College-level students often choose places far from their place of origin, so it becomes necessary to migrate to their destination of higher education. One of the reasons students migrate is that the quality of education in Indonesia needs to be evenly distributed. This happens because of universities.

Universities in Indonesia that fall into the quality higher education category are still dominated by universities on the island of Java (Rufaida & Kustanti, 2018)^[7]. This can be seen from Ristekdikti data in 2018, it is known that 8 of the ten best universities in Indonesia are on the island of Java. One of the destinations that is a regular destination for overseas students is Yogyakarta, which is known as the "City of Quality Education".

1. The provision of education in the City of Yogyakarta must have high quality standards and be leading in Southeast Asia;
2. Have a competitive advantage in mastering, utilizing, and developing technological knowledge;
3. Able to create a balance between intelligence (Intelligentia Quotient), emotional (Emotional Quotient), spiritual (Spiritual Quotient);
4. Developed with the support of a superior education policy system;
5. Provision of adequate educational facilities and infrastructure;
6. Creating a conducive educational atmosphere.

Apart from that, several factors make Yogyakarta an educational city, namely:

1. The aura of the palace influences the behavior of the people of Yogyakarta, who are calm, peaceful, and think realistically about the phenomena in Yogyakarta. So, every result of human thought is always imbued with cultural, social, and ethical values by developing a sense of culture. For example, the price of temporary housing, the price of daily living necessities, and the cost of helpful education are not based on economic principles. These conditions make Yogyakarta's climate safe and calm, and the community's trust in the palace provides an aura of mental calm so that study concentration can be focused. Atmospheric conditions like this differentiate students from other educational cities.
2. All fields of scientific discipline are presented in universities in Yogyakarta, both private and state schools.
3. Very complete and varied learning facilities and infrastructure also support Yogyakarta's success in becoming an "Education City", such as study centers, laboratories, libraries, museums, book markets, and a geographical location that is very profitable and easy to reach by various transportation.
4. Yogyakarta has many ancient names or nicknames, such as the city of tourism, city of culture, city of struggle, and city of "Comfortable Heart". This nickname indirectly complements the academic climate, which can be used as a study center and learning resource.
5. Other supporting factors that help strengthen the unique value of Yogyakarta, such as the birth of the oldest state university in Yogyakarta and the Father of National Education, Ki Hadjar Dewantoro, come from Yogyakarta. (Supardi, 2003)^[8]

As an educational city, Yogyakarta has many public and private universities. State Universities such as Gadjah Mada University, Yogyakarta State University, Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University, Yogyakarta Arts Institute and many private universities such as Indonesian Islamic University, Yogyakarta Muhammadiyah University, Atmajaya University, Sanata Dharma University, Taman Siswa University, University of Wacana Ambassador, Mercubuana University, YKPN College of Economics, STMIK AMIKOM and many more private universities in Yogyakarta. Plus, there are quite a lot of educational institutions spread throughout Yogyakarta.

City access Education brings students, and urban flow is relatively high. Urban flows come from various corners of Indonesia and abroad. One of the aims of the presence of urban currents is to make a living through business in the alternative economic field. Every year, many new students from various cities in Indonesia come to Yogyakarta to study and gain knowledge in the city of Yogyakarta. Based on statistical data from the provincial government of D.I. Yogyakarta, the number of students at D.I. Yogyakarta reaches 320,000 people, 90,000 or the equivalent of around 30% are students from outside the region (Zubaidah *et al.* 2015)^[11]. The urban flow in Yogyakarta turned out to be a generator of social change.

Yogyakarta as a "Culture Based Tourism" City is:

1. Tourism activities in the City of Yogyakarta are developed based on and centered on Javanese culture, which is in harmony with the history and culture of the Ngayogyakarta Hadiningrat Palace, local wisdom, and the noble values of national culture;
2. Perfect and increase the tourism cooperation network with other parties;
3. Become a leading tourist destination in Southeast Asia;
4. Increasing tourism activities is carried out by creating innovations that remain based on cultural tourism, historical building tourism, educational tourism, convection tourism, and shopping tourism;
5. Maintain and develop religious/religious norms in community life.

As a tourist destination city, Yogyakarta is crowded with tourists from within and outside the country every year. Yogyakarta has its attraction for tourists, so that the level of tourist visits has increased from year to year.

With such a large number of those being new people/immigrants who do not know anything about Yogyakarta, it is an obligation for the Yogyakarta Government to provide sources of information that can represent all information about Yogyakarta starting from

1. Place of Education: UGM, UNY, UIN, UII, UMY, USD, Atmajaya University, STIE YKPN, STMIK AKAKOM, and so on. Location and transportation routes to important locations.
2. Tourist Attractions: Temple Tourism, Beach Tourism, Nature Tourism, Sports Tourism, Historical Tourism, Pilgrimage Tourism, Architectural Tourism, Arts and Cultural Performances
3. Community Culture
4. Hospital
5. Hotel
6. Transportation
7. Arts: Dance, Karawitan, Gamelan, Shadow Puppetry, Wayang Orang
8. Performing Arts: Ramayana
8. museum
9. Beach
10. Palace
11. Big City
12. Silver Crafts, Pottery
13. Batik
14. Historic Places and so on.

All this information is gathered so that people can visit one location, and they will know globally about Yogyakarta. Building a "Window of Jogja" Library and empowering the

community is an idea to collect, preserve, present, and serve as a promotional forum for Yogyakarta. As Miniatur Yogyakarta or Taman Mini Yogyakarta.

The "Window of Jogja" library was designed to highlight cultural, religious, and philosophical elements. For example, in Yogyakarta, the existence of a Philosophical Axis and an Imaginary Axis can be used as a basis for creating the "Window of Jogja" Library. Philosophical Axis, the unity between Tugu Pal Putih (famous as Tugu Jogja) – and Kraton – Panggung Krapyak creates a straight line. Meanwhile, the Imaginary Axis, Mount Merapi – Kraton – South Sea in one series.

In building the "Window of Jogja" Library, everything about Yogyakarta is included: historical places, Kota Gede, Borobudur Temple, Prambanan Temple, Monuments, Beaches, Kraton, Malioboro, Vredeburg Fort, Great Mosque, UGM, Ramayana Ballet, Jogja Return Monument, Architectural buildings, unique communities, typical food and so on. Then, it is equipped with collections and information, both printed and soft files, offline and online. (Design Image Following).

Community Empowerment, to create a learning society, a long-life education, a literacy society, and a public reading society, increasing people's interest in reading and making people's lives brighter, especially in Yogyakarta and Indonesia. The role of librarians is vast, involving all activities in realizing the "Window of Jogja". Librarians socialize and inspire enthusiasm, making the public aware of the importance of science and technology. The public needs to pay attention to current information developments. With awareness of the importance of science and technology will grow and improve the welfare of society itself. It is hoped that it will increase people's reading interest, so the source that states that Yogyakarta people's reading interest is 0.18 needs to be corrected.

We hope the two concepts presented above can be an alternative to preserving cultural values as national heritage whose integrity and sustainability will be maintained from the perspective of Yogyakarta's unique features.

Conclusion

1. Yogyakarta as a Special City. Unique in history, art, culture, society, heritage, education, and tourism, which must be protected and preserved.
2. Librarians must participate in the arts, preserve the culture and all the privileges that exist as a heritage treasure that cannot be extinguished, and involve the community in this preservation.
3. One step to preserve this privilege is to design the "Window of Jogja" library and empower the community.
4. The "Window of Jogja" library displays all the treasures in Yogyakarta from the North, Central, South, and West to East sides of Yogyakarta. Starting from Mount Merapi, Mount Merapi Museum, Jogja Lagi Monument, Tugu, Malioboro, Fort Vredeburg, Palace, Kota Gede, Parangtritis Beach, Tombs of the Kings. From the East side, Prambanan Temple, Boko Temple to Borobudur; Transportation, Educational Places, Javanese Cultural Customs, Typical Food: gudeg, bakpia, Batik Clothing, Beskap and so on

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